

Unveiling Triad Dimensions: Background Characteristics, Learning Attitude, and English Proficiency of Junior High School Students in Far-Flung Area

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Abstract

In remote and far-flung area, Junior High School students navigated unique challenges that shape their educational experiences, particularly in learning English. Their background characteristics played a crucial role in developing their language attitude and proficiency. Thus, this study employed descriptive-correlational research design investigated the triad dimensions of background characteristics, learning attitude and English proficiency of junior high school students in a far-flung area. The study was conducted among the Grade 7 to Grade 10 students of Datu Ampak Kawan National High School in Basag, Senator Ninoy Aquino, Sultan Kudarat utilizing total enumeration sampling. Further, the study used the validated researcher-made questionnaire for English proficiency, and adopted questionnaire for learning attitude.

Findings revealed that the students were predominantly female; majority speak Visayan; have workbooks/LAS as common materials read; television as the most frequently used media; and

majority of parents have a high school level and below educational attainment. Students generally hold moderately positive attitudes towards English, and demonstrated average proficiency in vocabulary and grammar, but low proficiency in reading comprehension and reading fluency.

Findings further revealed a moderate positive correlation between learning attitude and overall English proficiency. Meanwhile, significant differences observed between various indicators in learning attitude and English proficiency and background characteristics. The study concluded that socioeconomic factors, particularly parental education, played a significant role in reading comprehension development. Recommendations included implementing literacy enrichment programs, promoting diverse reading materials, encouraging active language use, providing targeted grammar instruction for specific student groups, and engaging parents in their children's education.

Keywords: *Triad dimension, background characteristics, learning attitude, English proficiency, junior high school students in far-flung area*

Introduction

Proficiency in English stands as a cornerstone of academic success and professional advancement in today's interconnected world. As educational institutions increasingly adopt English as the medium of instruction, understanding the varying levels of proficiency among students becomes essential.

In the context of globalization, English proficiency is a significant indicator of academic success (Thompson et. al., 2023). Basically, English has become the dominant language of academic communication, particularly in international contexts (Bianco, 2016). More importantly, is the dominance of English in academia, thus, learners need to be proficient to understand lectures, write papers and engage in discussion (Yuksel, 2023). The reasons that Serquina (2018) concerned, having English as a medium of instruction, significant English language difficulties due to different factors are likely to hinder learners' progress in other subjects.

The purpose of this study is to identify the sentiments of the teachers in terms of the learning proficiency and attitudes of the students have been perennial despite various remediation conducted in school. One thing that has not yet tested is the actual investigation of the problem in terms of the students' background characteristics such as gender, first language use, availability of learning materials, and the educational attainment of the parents on how it may influence their learning attitude and somehow affect their learning proficiency on grammar, vocabulary, reading fluency and comprehension. Through the results of the study, a reinforced competency plan is being proposed. Hence, this study is conducted.

Further, this study highlights the urgent need for improved English language proficiency programs in far-flung areas, emphasizing both educational and economic benefits. Through this study, the contextual gap observed on the limited study on the specific population and geography; and the knowledge gap on the specific root of the language proficiency problem of the learners may be addressed.

Statement of the Problem (SOP)

This study aimed to determine the background characteristics, learning attitude and English proficiency of Junior High school students in far-flung area as basis for the development of reinforced competency plan.

Specifically, this intended to answer the following questions:

1. What is the background characteristics of the junior high school students in terms of:
 - 1.1 Gender;
 - 1.2 First language used;
 - 1.3 Reading materials used;
 - 1.4 Types of media exposure; and,
 - 1.5 Highest educational attainment of parents/guardians?
2. What is the learning attitude of Junior High School students in far-flung area in terms of:
 - 2.1 Affective;
 - 2.2 Behavioral; and,
 - 2.3 Cognitive?

3. What is the level of English language proficiency of the junior high school students in terms of:
 - 3.1 Vocabulary;
 - 3.2 Grammar;
 - 3.3 Reading Fluency; and,
 - 3.4 Reading Comprehension?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the learning attitude and level of English proficiency of Junior High School students in far-flung area?
5. Is there a significant difference between the learning attitude when categorized to the background characteristics of Junior High School students in far-flung area?
6. Is there a significant difference between the level of English proficiency when categorized to the background characteristics of Junior High School students in far-flung area?
7. What reinforced competency development plan can be developed to enhance the English proficiency of Junior High School students?

Methodology

This study employed a descriptive-correlational design, as outlined by Creswell (2014). This method is ideal for exploring the connections and patterns among different factors without directly influencing them. It allowed for a thorough examination of how English proficiency levels relate to other variables within the natural context of the students' learning environment.

The population of the study included the one hundred twenty-three(123) Grades 7-10 students from Datu Ampak Kawan National High School, Basag, Senator Ninoy Aquino, Sultan Kudarat enrolled in the school year 2024-2025.

The research instruments assessed the proficiency of Grades 7-10 in English, which was measured using the survey test. The questionnaire which is a profiling instrument was used to obtain the learner-profile variables namely, gender, first language used, reading materials used, types of media exposure, and parents' educational attainment. The design of this instrument was adapted from Crisostomo (2007), although certain changes were introduced. The test on vocabulary and grammar adapted from Manuel (2022), reading fluency and reading comprehension was prepared by the researcher. It was comprised of sixty (60) multiple choice questions, equally distributed to test students' Proficiency in English and an additional of fifteen (15) questions in components of attitudes survey test adapted from Makhtuna (2021). It was anchored on the DepEd No. 34 for the School Year 2024-2025, The Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs) of the DepEd Grades 7-10 Modules.

The following hypotheses were formulated based on the concepts of the study that the researcher conducted.

Ho₁: There is a significant relationship between the learning attitude variables and the English language proficiency of the Junior High School attitudes.

- Ho₂: There is no significant difference between the background characteristics variables and the Learning Attitude of the Junior High School students in the far-flung area in terms of gender, first language used, reading materials used, types of media exposure, and highest educational attainment of parents or guardians.
- Ho₃: There is no significant difference between the background characteristics variables and the English language proficiency of the Junior High School students in the far-flung area in terms of gender, first language used, reading materials used, types of media exposure, and highest educational attainment of parents or guardians.

Results and Discussion

The results of the background characteristics of the Junior High School in far-flung area in terms of gender, first language, reading materials used, media exposure, and parents/guardians educational attainment. Learning attitude in terms of affective, behavioral and cognitive. And English proficiency in terms of vocabulary, grammar, reading comprehension, and reading fluency. The following tables present the result of the findings.

SOP1. Table 1. Background Characteristics of Junior High School students in terms of Gender, First Language Used, Reading Materials Used, Types of Media Exposure, and Educational Attainment of Parents or Guardians.

Gender	Frequency	Percentage(%)
Male	53	43.1
Female	70	56.9
First Language Used		
Non-Visayan	25	20.3
Visayan	98	79.7
Reading Material Used		
Workbooks	70	56.9
Textbooks	21	17.1
Information Resources (Magazine, Newspaper, Digital Resources)	32	26
Types of Media Exposure		
Television	64	52
Radio	28	22.8

Digital Learning Devices	31	25.2
Educational Attainment of Parents/Guardians		
High School Level and below	70	56.9
High School Graduate and Higher Level	53	43.1

The sample consists of 123 students, with 53 (43.1%) male and 70 (56.9) female students. As indicated, there is a slightly higher proportion of female students (56.9%) compared to male students (43.1%). The table shows that Visayan was the dominant first language among the students, spoken by 79.7% of the students. Only 20.3% of students spoke Non-Visayan languages.

It can be gleaned that the workbooks/LAS were the most frequently used reading material (56.9%), followed by magazines, newspapers, and digital resources (26%). Textbooks were used by a smaller percentage (17.1%). As the result of this study conveys, television is the most prevalent media source (52%), followed by computers (25.2%) and radio (22.8%). The majority of parents (56.9%) have a high school level education or below, while (43.1%) a high school graduate and higher level degree.

SOP2 Table 2. Level of Learning Attitude of Junior High School Students in terms of Affective, Behavioral and Cognitive

Areas	Mean	SD	Description	Interpretation Ratings
Affective	3.11	0.18	Moderately Positive	Level of attitude is moderately positive
Behavioral	2.55	0.52	Moderately Positive	Level of attitude is moderately positive
Cognitive	3.09	0.38	Moderately Positive	Level of attitude is moderately positive
Mean	2.91	0.29	Moderately Positive	Level of attitude is moderately positive

Students demonstrated a positive learning attitude across all three areas (affective, behavioral, and cognitive), with a total mean score of 2.91 with a total standard deviation of 0.29. This suggests that they generally have moderate positive feelings towards the language, are willing to use it, and believe it is important.

SOP3. Table 3. Level of English Language Proficiency of the Junior High School Students in terms of Vocabulary, Grammar, Reading Comprehension, and Reading Fluency

Areas	Mean Ratings	SD	Description
Vocabulary	46.50	24.55	Average Proficiency
Grammar	38.10	20.97	Average Proficiency
Reading Comprehension	32.36	15.05	Low Proficiency
Reading Fluency	33.07	17.93	Low Proficiency
Mean	38.97	17.55	Average Proficiency

The students demonstrated average proficiency in English overall mean score of 38.97 with a standard deviation of 17.55. However, there are significant variations across different skills: Vocabulary has an average proficiency with a mean score of 46.50 and standard deviation of 24.25; Grammar has an average proficiency with a mean score of 38.10 and a standard deviation of 20.97; Reading Comprehension has a low proficiency with mean score of 32.36 and standard deviation of 15.05; and, Reading Fluency has a low proficiency with a mean score of 33.07 and a standard deviation of 17.93.

SOP4. Table 4. Test of Relationship Between the Students' Learning Attitude and Level of English Proficiency

Variables	r-value Pearson r	Interpretation	p-value	Interpretation
Language Attitude * English Proficiency	.447**	Moderate Positive	.000	Significant
Affective * Vocabulary	.252**	Weak Positive	.005	Significant
Affective * Grammar	.203*	Weak Positive	.024	Significant
Affective * Reading Comprehension	.103	Very Weak Positive	.257	Not Significant
Affective * Reading Fluency	.361**	Weak Positive	.000	Significant
Behavioral * Vocabulary	.353**	Weak Positive	.000	Significant
Behavioral * Grammar	.385**	Weak Positive	.000	Significant
Behavioral * Reading Comprehension	.377**	Weak Positive	.000	Significant

Behavioral * Reading Fluency	.737**	Strong Positive	000	Significant
Cognitive * Vocabulary	.295**	Weak Positive	001	Significant
Cognitive * Grammar	.338**	Weak Positive	000	Significant
Cognitive * Reading Comprehension	.253**	Weak Positive	005	Significant
Cognitive * Reading Fluency	.590**	Moderate Positive	000	Significant

There is a moderate positive relationship between learning attitude and overall English proficiency (r-value = .447, p-value = .000). Significant positive relationships existed between learning attitude and proficiency in vocabulary, grammar, and reading fluency. However, the relationship between learning attitude and reading comprehension was very weak and does not show any significant relationship.

SOP5.Table 5. Test of Difference Between the Learning Attitude when Categorized to the Background Characteristics of Junior High School students in Far-Flung Area in Terms of Gender

Learning Attitude Indicators	Group	Mean	SD	t-value	p-	Interpretation
Affective	Male	3.11	.17	2.381	.060	.953
	Female	3.11	.19			
Behavioral	Male	2.42	.51	2.381	.019	Significant
	Female	2.64	.50			
Cognitive	Male	3.07	.38	.367	.714	Not Significant
	Female	3.10	.38			
Overall Language Attitude	Male	2.87	.29	1.533	.128	Not Significant
	Female	2.95	.29			

The table shows that there is a significant difference between learning attitude and the gender of students on either male or female. Males has a lower mean score in behavioral learning attitude compared to females.

However, there were no significant differences in affective, cognitive, or overall learning attitude. The data was analyzed using an independent samples t-test to determine if there is a significant difference between the two groups.

Table 6. Test of Difference Between the Learning Attitude when Categorized to the Background Characteristics of the Junior High School Students in Far-Flung Area in terms of First Language Used

Learning Attitude Indicators	Group	Mean	SD	t-value	p-value	Interpretation
Affective	Non-Visayan	3.09	.12	.688	.492	Not Significant
	Visayan	3.12	.20			
Behavioral	Non-Visayan	2.54	.48	.125	.901	Not Significant
	Visayan	2.55	.53			
Cognitive	Non-Visayan	3.02	.34	1.037	.302	Not Significant
	Visayan	3.10	.39			
Overall Language Attitude	Non-Visayan	2.88	.24	.662	.509	Not Significant
	Visayan	2.92	.30			

There is no significant differences between learning attitude and first language used by the students who either speak Visayan or Non-visayan languages with an overall language attitude mean of 2.92 and standard deviation of .30 as shown on the table.

Table 7. Test of Difference Between the Learning Attitude when Categorized to the Background Characteristics of the Junior High School Students in Far-Flung Area in terms of Reading Materials Used

Learning Attitude Indicators	Group	Mean	SD	F- value	p- value	Interpretation
Affective	Workbook/LAS	3.09	.18	1.691	.189	Not Significant
	Textbook	3.16	.23			
	Magazines, Newspaper and Digital Resources	3.13	.16			

Behavioral	Workbook/LAS	2.56	.51	1.531	220	Not Significant
	Textbook	2.38	.55			
	Magazines, Newspaper and Digital Resources	2.63	.50			
Cognitive	Workbook/LAS	3.07	.37	.840	.434	Not Significant
	Textbook	3.03	.35			
	Magazines, Newspaper and Digital Resources	3.16	.42			
Overall Language Attitude	Workbook/LAS	2.91	.29	1.040	.356	Not Significant
	Textbook	2.86	.30			
	Magazines, Newspaper and Digital Resources	2.97	.29			

As presented in table 7, there is no significant difference between learning attitude and students' reading materials such as workbooks/LAS, textbooks, or magazines, newspapers, and digital resources. Differences among the three groups were analyzed using a one-way ANOVA.

Table 8. Test of Difference Between the Learning Attitude when Categorized to the Background Characteristics of the Junior High School Students in terms in Far-Flung Area in terms of Type of Media Exposure

Learning Attitude Indicators	Group	Mean	SD	F-value	p-value	Interpretation
Affective	Television	3.12	.18	.793	.455	Not Significant
	Radio	3.1	.17			
	Computer	3.08	.20			
Behavioral	Television	2.55	.49	1.667	.193	Not Significant
	Radio	2.41	.53			
	Computer	2.66	.55			

	Television	3.02	.27			
Cognitive	Radio	3.11	.42	2.689	.072	Not Significant
	Computer	3.21	.49			
	Overall	Television	2.90			
Language Attitude	Radio	2.89	.32	1.070	.346	Not Significant
	Computer	2.98	.35			

As noted, there is no significant difference between language attitude and students' media exposure on the television, radio, or computers. This suggests that the types of media exposure do not significantly impact language attitude. Students who use different types of media seem to have similar feelings, behaviors, and perceptions towards language. This finding implies that language learning interventions can be designed to incorporate various media formats without significantly impacting student attitudes towards language.

Table 9. Test of Difference Between the Learning Attitude when Categorized to the Background Characteristics of the Junior High School Students in Far-Flung Area in terms of Highest Educational Attainment of Parents or Guardians

Learning Attitude Indicators	Group	Mean	SD	t-value	p-value	Interpretation
Affective	High School Level and Below	3.2	.20	.456	.649	Not Significant
	High School Graduate and higher level	3.10	.16			
Behavioral	High School Level and Below	2.56	.52	.306	.760	Not Significant
	High School Graduate and higher level	2.53	.51			
Cognitive	High School Level and Below	3.10	.40	.463	.644	Not Significant
	High School Graduate and higher level	3.07	.36			

Overall Language Attitude	High School Level and Below	2.93	.31	.473	.637	Not Significant
	High School Graduate and higher level	2.90	.27			

There is a significant difference in reading comprehension scores between students whose parents have attainment on either high school level and below or a high school graduate and higher level.. Students whose parents high school graduate and higher level scored higher in reading comprehension.

This finding suggests that parental educational attainment may play a role in influencing reading comprehension skills. Students whose parents have higher levels of education may have more exposure to literacy practices and resources, which could contribute to stronger reading comprehension. This may be due to factors like, parents with higher education levels may create more literacy-rich environments at home, with more books, reading activities, and discussions about reading.

SOP6. Table 10. Test of Difference Between the Level of English Proficiency when Categorized to the Background Characteristics of the Junior High School Students in Far-Flung Area in terms of Gender

English Proficiency Indicators	Group	Mean	SD	t-value	p-value	Interpretation
Vocabulary	Male	41.26	19.8	.2179	.031	Significant
	Female	50.48	27.04			
Grammar	Male	34.84	18.93	1.508	.134	Not Significant
	Female	40.57	22.21			
Reading Comprehension	Male	30.57	14.05	1.151	.252	Not Significant
	Female	33.71	15.72			
Reading Fluency	Male	30.13	18.81	1.593	.114	Not Significant
	Female	35.29	17.03			
Overall Proficiency	Male	35.56	14.73	1.966	.052	Not Significant
	Female	41.56	19.11			

Results entail that the results on the difference between the students' level of English proficiency and background characteristics vary based on their significance. There is a significant difference in vocabulary scores between male and female students, with females scoring higher compared to foundation, both genders may have similar levels of proficiency in other areas of English. This finding further highlights the

importance of targeting vocabulary development specifically for male students. It suggested that interventions should focus on expanding vocabulary knowledge to improve overall English proficiency.

Table 11. Test of Difference Between the Level of English Proficiency when Categorized to the Background Characteristics of the Junior High School Students in terms of First Language Used

English Proficiency Indicators	Group	Mean	SD	t-value	p-value	Interpretation
Vocabulary	Non-Visayan	41.60	25.26	1.120	.265	Not Significant
	Visayan	47.76	24.34			
Grammar	Non-Visayan	29.33	17.21	2.387	.019	Significant
	Visayan	40.34	21.33			
Reading Comprehension	Non-Visayan	29.07	15.14	1.228	.222	Not Significant
	Visayan	33.20	14.98			
Reading Fluency	Non-Visayan	33.31	17.74	.075	.940	Not Significant
	Visayan	33.01	18.14			
Overall Language Proficiency	Non-Visayan	33.24	15.54	1.8746	.067	Not Significant
	Visayan	40.43	17.81			

Overall result reveals no significant difference between students' English proficiency and background characteristics in language used. Nevertheless, specific results on each indicator shows a bit distinction. There is a significant difference between grammar scores and students

Students who speak Non-Visayan and Visayan languages, with Non-Visayan students scoring lower. However, there are no significant differences in vocabulary, reading comprehension, and reading fluency. It means that the language use of the students in far-flung area does not influence their English proficiency on these three indicators. On the other hand, while Non-Visayan students may have weaker grammar skills, both groups may have similar levels of proficiency in other areas of English. This finding highlighted the importance of providing targeted grammar instruction for Non-Visayan students. It suggested that interventions should focus on improving grammar skills to enhance overall English proficiency.

Table 12. Test of Difference Between the Level of English Proficiency when Categorized to the Background Characteristics of the Junior High School Students in terms of Reading Materials Used

English Proficiency Indicators	Group	Mean	SD	F-value	p-value	Interpretation
Vocabulary	Workbook/LAS	46.57	25.97	1.581	.210	Not Significant
	Textbook	39.05	24.06			
	Magazines, Newspaper and Digital Resources	51.25	20.91			
Grammar	Workbook/LAS	38.38	20.26	1.444	.240	Not Significant
	Textbook	31.75	22.79			
	Magazines, Newspaper and Digital Resources	41.67	21.01			
Reading Comprehension	Workbook/LAS	31.24	13.55	4.663	0.11	Not Significant
	Textbook	26.67	16.47			
	Magazines, Newspaper and Digital Resources	38.54	15.89			
Reading Fluency	Workbook/LAS	30.36	18.27	4.035	.020	Significant
	Textbook	30.59	16.78			
	Magazines, Newspaper and Digital Resources	40.63	16.15			
Overall Language Proficiency	Workbook/LAS	38.70	17.45	2.739	.069	Not Significant
	Textbook	32.49	18.49			
	Magazines, Newspaper and Digital Resources	43.82	16.15			

Similarly, overall result reveals no significant difference between students' English proficiency and background characteristics in reading materials used. Nevertheless, specific results on each indicator also shows a apparent distinction. There is significant difference between the students' English proficiency in reading fluency scores; and the use of workbooks/LAS, textbooks, or magazines, newspapers, and digital resources. Students who used magazines, newspapers, and digital resources scored higher in both areas. It is manifested that learning materials are truly vital to aid the learning competency of the students.

Table 13. Test of Difference Between the Level of English Proficiency when Categorized to the Background Characteristics of the Junior High School Students in Far-Flung Area in terms of Type of Media Exposure

English Proficiency Indicators	Group	Mean	SD	F-value	p-value	Interpretation
Vocabulary	Television	45.94	24.38	.037	.964	Not Significant
	Radio	46.90	24.91			
	Computer	47.31	25.38			
Grammar	Television	39.17	19.57	1.037	.345	Not Significant
	Radio	33.10	21.58			
	Computer	40.43	23.09			
Reading Comprehension	Television	33.23	14.76	1.177	.312	Not Significant
	Radio	28.57	15.49			
	Computer	33.98	15.13			
Reading Fluency	Television	32.77	14.71	2.075	.130	Not Significant
	Radio	28.45	21.84			
	Computer	37.85	19.50			
Overall Language Proficiency	Television	39.44	17.02	.520	.596	Not Significant
	Radio	36.11	19.65			
	Computer	40.57	17.91			

As noted, there is no significant difference between language attitude and students' media exposure on the television, radio, or computers. This suggests that the types of media exposure do not significantly impact language attitude. Students who use different types of media seem to have similar feelings, behaviors, and perceptions towards language. This finding implies that language learning interventions can be designed to incorporate various media formats without significantly impacting student attitudes towards language.

Table 14. Test of Difference between the Level of English Proficiency when Categorized to the Background Characteristics of the Junior High School Students in Far-Flung Area in terms of Highest Educational Attainment of Parents or Guardians

English Proficiency Indicators	Group	Mean	SD	t-value	p-value	Interpretation
Vocabulary	High School Level and Below	45.52	25.81	.507	.613	Not Significant
	High School Graduate and higher level	47.80	22.97			
Grammar	High School Level and Below	37.24	22.28	.524	.601	Not Significant
	High School Graduate and higher level	39.25	19.24			
Reading Comprehension	High School Level and Below	29.52	13.83	2.449	.016	Significant
	High School Graduate and higher level	36.10	15.88			
Reading Fluency	High School Level and Below	33.45	20.08	.269	.789	Not Significant
	High School Graduate and higher level	32.57	14.80			
Overall Language Proficiency	High School Level and Below	37.40	18.34	1.144	.255	Not Significant
	High School Graduate and higher level	41.05	16.38			

There is a significant difference in reading comprehension scores between students whose parents have attainment on either high school level and below or a high school graduate and higher level.. Students whose parents high school graduate and higher level scored higher in reading comprehension. This finding suggests that parental educational attainment may play a role in influencing reading comprehension skills. Students whose parents have higher levels of education may have more exposure to literacy practices and resources, which could contribute to stronger reading comprehension. This may be due to factors like, parents with higher education levels may create more literacy-rich environments at home, with more books, reading activities, and discussions about reading.

SOP7. Reinforced Competency (RiCo) Development Plan to Enhance the English Proficiency and Learning Attitude of the Junior High School Students in Far-flung Area

English proficiency and learning attitude play a crucial role in the academic success of junior high school students, especially those in far-flung areas where access to quality educational resources may be limited. Many students in these areas face challenges in reading comprehension, fluency, and grammar, often influenced by their learning environment, parental education, and available reading materials. Additionally, while students may hold positive cognitive and affective attitudes toward English, their behavioral engagement in language use remains low, creating a gap between perception and practice.

To address these concerns, a Reinforced Competency (RiCo) Development Plan is essential to provide targeted interventions, diversified learning strategies, and enhanced instructional support. By integrating interactive reading activities, technology-based resources, and structured competency-building programs, this initiative aims to improve students' overall English proficiency and active language engagement, ensuring better learning outcomes despite geographical and resource constraints.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the results, the following conclusions are hereby formulated:

A key realization is that while students may hold positive perceptions of English, this does not always translate into active engagement and proficiency, highlighting the need for instructional strategies that bridge the gap between attitude and actual language use. The study also reinforces the idea that access to diverse and meaningful reading materials plays a crucial role in improving reading comprehension and fluency, suggesting that relying solely on traditional workbooks may not be enough to develop strong literacy skills. Furthermore, the influence of parental education on comprehension skills underscores the importance of home literacy practices in language development, suggesting that family involvement should be a focus in language education programs.

From a broader perspective, these findings contribute new knowledge to the interplay between behavioral attitudes and language proficiency, particularly the strong connection between active language engagement and comprehension skills. This highlights the need for teaching approaches that prioritize interactive and applied learning experiences, ensuring that students not only understand English but also use it in meaningful contexts. In terms of educational policy, the results support the importance of improving students' exposure to diverse learning materials and fostering a literacy-rich environment both at home and in school. For future research, this study underscores the need for further investigation into how digital

resources, media exposure, and family literacy practices shape language proficiency over time, contributing to a more holistic understanding of language learning in various educational settings.

RECOMMENDATIONS

From the findings and conclusions derived from the study, the following recommendations are presented:

1. The school may implement a more diverse and engaging reading program. Since most students primarily speak Visayan and rely on television as their main media exposure, integrating bilingual and multimedia-assisted learning strategies can help bridge the gap between their first language and English proficiency. Additionally, parental involvement may be strengthened, providing resources and guidance to parents especially those with lower educational attainment on how they can support their children's literacy development at home.

2. The school may implement interactive and immersive English activities, such as debates, role-playing, and language clubs, to encourage students to actively use the language in real-life contexts. This may help bridge the gap between their positive attitude toward English and their actual engagement, reinforcing both confidence and proficiency.

3. Language teachers may implement targeted reading interventions that focus on enhancing comprehension and fluency through guided reading, interactive discussions, and exposure to diverse texts. Incorporating engaging reading strategies may help students develop deeper understanding and more fluent reading skills.

4. Language teachers may design learning activities that actively engage students in using English, such as collaborative projects, storytelling, and real-world communication tasks, to strengthen their behavioral learning attitude. By fostering consistent language practice and meaningful interaction, students can enhance their reading comprehension, fluency, and overall English proficiency.

5. The schools may provide additional grammar support for Non-Visayan students through targeted instruction and practice exercises to strengthen their language foundation. Additionally, promoting diverse reading materials such as magazines, newspapers, and digital resources, along with parental literacy workshops, can enhance students' reading comprehension and fluency regardless of their background.

6. The schools may consider incorporating strategies that cater to the unique language backgrounds of your students. This could involve providing additional support for students who are learning English as a second language, using visual aids and other strategies to make learning more accessible, and incorporating more opportunities for students to practice their grammar skills in real-world contexts.

7. The schools may implement and sustain the reinforced competency plan being developed out of the result of this study. This plan may strengthen the inclusion of interactive learning strategies, enhanced reading programs, and teacher training to ensure that students receive comprehensive support in improving their English proficiency.

8. Other researchers may consider a new type of research to venture such as Qualitative methods like interviews or focus groups to gain a deeper understanding of students' experiences, perceptions, and motivations.

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